

DENSIFICATION OF Al_4SiC_4 -SiC CONTAINING TYRANNO-SA SiC FIBER

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1 Introduction

SiC has unique combination of properties such as high strength, elastic modulus, hardness, tribological properties, chemical and radiation resistance [1]. However, its industrial application has been limited so far partly due to the high production cost originating from sintering process at high temperature/pressure. Consequently, low temperature sintering has been challenging topics of SiC during the last decades [2-3].

SiC_{fiber}/SiC long fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CMC) has recently attracted strong attention due to the potential application in the field of next-generation energy generation such as fusion reactors, 4th generation nuclear reactors and high efficiency gas turbines. CMC made using chemical vapour infiltration (CVI) and hot pressing (HP) method has been reputed to be appropriate for the application under high temperature, pressure and neutron irradiation.

Various types of SiC_{fiber}/SiC CMC has been produced by NITE (nano-infiltration transient eutectic phase) process. In the process, Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 and SiO_2 (or MgO) has been used as sintering additives [4]. The ternary additive system requires fairly high temperature for the densification of nano-SiC ($\geq 1700^\circ C$), and the components may interact each other during slurry preparation. Accordingly, development of a new additive system which can solve the problems of NITE process has been required.

The present authors used Al_4SiC_4 as a sintering additive of SiC and achieved the low temperature sintering of SiC [5]. In spite of the beneficial properties of the additive, however,

the densification behavior of SiC using the additive has not been systematically analyzed when high quality SiC fibers were introduced.

In this report, Al_4SiC_4 was used as a sintering additive of SiC. The effects of additive content and sintering temperature, pressure, time on the relative density was analyzed. Also, the damage of pyrocarbon coated Tyranno-SA fibers during densification of SiC was investigated.

2 Experimental procedure

Tyranno-SA fibers coated with pyro-carbon were used for the testing. Matrix material was sub-micrometer scale UF-15 SiC containing Al_4SiC_4 as a sintering additive.

Metal Al (Alfa Aesar), Si (Vesta, Sicomil, Grade 4), and C (carbon black, Alfa Aesar) were used as the starting powders. The Al, Si and C powders (4 Al : Si : 4 C by molar ratio) were mixed in ethyl alcohol for 10 min using an ultrasonifier, and the mixed slurries were dried with stirring using a rotary evaporator. Then, the powder mixtures were calcined at $1150^\circ C$ for 5 min. in Ar (heating rate: 50 K/min.) using SPS. The calcined Al_4SiC_4 powder was mixed with α -SiC (UF-15, H. C. Starck) using a planetary mill with SiC ball, SiC jar and ethyl alcohol at 200 – 300 revolutions per minute (r.p.m.) for 12 - 24 h.

Then, the slurries were dried with stirring using a rotary evaporator, and the obtained powder mixtures were sieved and densified by SPS (Dr. Sinter SCM 4000, Sumitomo Coal Mining Co. Ltd.). One-dimensional (1D-) fiber-reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CMC) composed of Tyranno-SA SiC fibers (UBE) with C coating and SiC matrix (termed SiC_f/SiC) were fabricated. The fibers were placed in the middle of the powder mixture composed of SiC

and Al_4SiC_4 . Then, the graphite mold containing the powder and the fibers was tapped to enhance the filling of the powder into the interstices between the fibers, and was heated at 1600 - 2400°C under 20 – 40 MPa pressure.

Relative density of the sintered specimens was measured using Archimedes' method. The cross-section of the SiC_f/SiC was polished up to 1 μm finish using diamond slurry and the properties of the specimens were analyzed using X-ray with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Part of the CMC specimens were fractured in order to analyze fiber pull-out behavior.

3 Results

Table 1 summarized the relative density of SiC after sintering with changing the amount of Al_4SiC_4 , sintering temperature, time and pressure. Pure SiC was not rapidly densified even at 2400°C under 40MPa pressure, and the relative density was only 83.9% after sintering for 3 min. Densification did not strongly occur at 1850 °C when the additive content was 0.25wt%.

Table 1. Relative density of sintered SiC.

Al_4SiC_4 (wt%)	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)	Pressure (MPa)	R. D. (%)
0	2400	3	40	83.9
0.25	1850	60	40	73.0
0.5	1800	120	40	97.9
1	1750	60	30	96.0
2	1700	60	30	97.5
10	1600	30	30	95.1
12.5	1600	30	20	96.4

In contrast, highly dense SiC was obtained at 1800°C when adding 0.5wt% of Al_4SiC_4 . The sintering temperature to obtain dense specimens decreased to 1700°C by increasing additive content to 2wt%. The results clearly indicated the high efficiency of Al_4SiC_4 as a sintering additive of SiC. Sintering temperature to obtain dense SiC decreased further to 1600°C when adding 12.5wt% of Al_4SiC_4 .

Fig. 1 shows the shrinkage of SiC during sintering under various temperature and pressure conditions with changing the additive content. The onset

temperature of shrinkage increased from 1590°C to 1650°C when reducing the additive content from 10wt% to 0.5wt%. Shrinkage occurred continuously during sintering at and below 1650°C in case the additive content was higher than 1 wt%.

Fig. 1. Shrinkage of SiC with changing additive content, sintering temperature and pressure.

Lee *et al.* reported that the possible sintering mechanism of Al_4SiC_4 -SiC system is the modification of the properties of the grain boundaries by the Al activator which enhanced grain boundary diffusion [5].

Fig. 2 is the SiC_f/SiC after sintering at 1800 °C using 1wt% of Al_4SiC_4 . Nearly fully dense SiC matrix could be observed (Fig. 2 (a), (b)). In spite of the low additive content, strong deformation of the fibers was observed (Fig. 2 (c)). Also, the pull-out of fibers did not strongly occur in the fractured surface (Fig. 2 (a)). The results indicated that the deformation of SiC fiber and the reaction between the fiber and matrix to form strong interface occurred at 1800 °C when adding small amount of Al_4SiC_4 .

Fig. 3 is the SiC fibers embedded within sintered SiC containing 4 and 10wt% Al_4SiC_4 . The deterioration of pyro-carbon coating, deformation of SiC fiber and sintering reaction between the fiber and matrix occurred in the specimen sintered at 1650°C under 30MPa pressure (Fig. 3 (a)). As a result, the CMC did not show fiber pull-out behavior.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2. Morphology of SiC_f/SiC containing 1wt% Al₄SiC₄ after sintering at 1800 °C for 2h under 40MPa pressure.

In contrast, pyro-carbon coating was not strongly damaged at 1600°C (Fig. 3 (b), (c)). The resultant CMC did not show brittle trans-granular fracture behavior. However, the deformation of Tyrano-SA fiber began to occur even at this condition. The additive not only promoted the densification of SiC matrix, but also induced the deformation of SiC fiber. Investigation is going on in order to optimize sintering condition for the preparation of SiC_f/SiC CMC using Al₄SiC₄ sintering additive.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Morphology of SiC_f/SiC sintered at (a) 1650°C, 30min, 30MPa, 4wt% Al₄SiC₄ (b), (c) 1600°C, 30min, 30MPa, 10wt% Al₄SiC₄.

(c)

Fig. 3. (c) *Continued.*

4 Conclusions

Al_4SiC_4 was used as a sintering additive of SiC. Dense SiC was obtained after SPS at 1600 – 1800°C when using 0.5 – 10wt% Al_4SiC_4 . In spite of the high efficiency as a sintering additive of SiC, the additive rather strongly deteriorated pyro-carbon coating and promoted the deformation of SiC fiber.

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